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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**4. The Peculiarities of Inter-Institutional
Interaction of Transregional Cooperation Legal
Regulation: Trends in the Contemporary EU. By
VIKTOR SHCHERBAK and others, p. 80.**

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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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**THE PECULIARITIES OF INTER-INSTITUTIONAL
INTERACTION OF TRANSREGIONAL
COOPERATION LEGAL REGULATION: TRENDS IN
THE CONTEMPORARY EU**

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ABSTRACT

The subject of the study is the legal opening of innovative technologies that optimise access to the opportunity to exchange new approaches in managing the development of the EU and neighbouring territories. The methodological basis of the study is methods of document analysis, the study of EC treaties, official declarations, laws, regulations and directives. It also includes an analysis of official reports and documents of EU institutions, such as the European Commission, the European Parliament, and the Council of the European Union. The article aims to establish the peculiarities of inter-institutional interaction within the framework of transnational cooperation in the modern EU. Results of the study showed that the European Neighborhood and Partnership Policy includes programmes aimed at promoting the economic and social development of regions bordering the EU and stimulating cooperation with regions of third countries and established that legal regulation of transregional cooperation ensures the formation of coordination and coordination structures. The European legal regulation practices consider the specificity of the subregions approved. It was found that transregional cooperation acquires an authentic expression due to the flexibility of legal regulation in media interaction. Cyber security was discussed as one of the leading factors in increasing the effectiveness of transregional cooperation between Ukraine and the EU in the face of a Russian invasion. In conclusion, the planned indicators of contemporary EU development legislation consider the diversity of the definition of leadership industries and the distribution of positive experiences.

Keywords: transnational cooperation, EU legislation, European neighbourhood policy.

1: INTRODUCTION

The legal regulation of transregional cooperation in the contemporary EU aims to increase the efficiency of social, economic and cultural transactions in the conditions of the crises caused by COVID-19 and the Russian-Ukrainian war. It takes on the importance of reducing bureaucratic obstacles. Optimising access to innovative technologies opens the opportunity for new approaches to exchange in managing the development of territories. Contemporary EU has become the subject of law-making activity there, political interactions at the level of member states and the level of institutions of supranational governance; the European Commission and the European Parliament pay considerable attention to interregional cooperation, it acts as one the drivers of internal integration, as it provides for horizontal cross-border interaction due to the improvement of legal regulation of transregional cooperation is ensured institutionalisation of interregional clusters, as well as the legal framework of the EU, supplies a standard for transregional relations, which includes a set of development indicators and benchmarks for member countries and

neighbouring countries. As a result, the level of development of specific regions, territories, and communities has increased to the European level. The actual task of this study is to identify the peculiarities of the transformation of the EU's neighbourhood policy, as well as the newest tools for stimulating transregional development. Identifying the peculiarities of legal regulation and transnationalism of cooperation provides the latest approaches for specific projects in energy and the crowdfunding of transport connections. Cases of legal regulation of transregional cooperation enrich public management with decision-making experience in crisis conditions and demonstrate means of improving management efficiency.

Literature review

The EU legal norms provide clear frameworks and guiding principles that help define interregional cooperation's scope, nature, and procedures. For this reason, interregional cooperation has become the research subject for many contemporary scholars.

Several issues within this research area have been explored in the works of Braun¹ (political dimensions of policy coordination in the spheres of knowledge and innovation), Capello and Lenzi² (long-term influence of regional learning paradigms on innovation policy), Maggioni and Uberti³ (arguing that both physical proximity and relational proximity are critically crucial for effective knowledge exchange), Mariussen et al.⁴ (promoting strategies of smart specialisation), and Puukka⁵. Radosevic and Ciampi Stancova⁶ identify key factors influencing interregional and transnational cooperation, while Uyarra et al.⁷ study the external orientation of innovative specialisation strategies.

¹ D. Braun, "Organising the political coordination of knowledge and innovation policies", *Science and Public Policy*, Vol. 35, No. 4 (2008), pp. 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.3152/030234208X287056>

² R. Capello and C. Lenzi, "Persistence in regional learning paradigms and trajectories: Consequences for innovation policy design", *European Planning Studies*, Vol. 24, No. 9 (2016), pp. 1587–1604. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2016.1177493>

³ M. A. Maggioni and T. E. Uberti, "Knowledge networks across Europe: which distance matters?", *The Annals of Regional Science*, Vol. 43 (2009), pp. 691–720. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00168-008-0254-7>

⁴ A. Mariussen, R. Rakhmatullin and L. Stanionyte, *Smart Specialisation: Creating Growth through Transnational Cooperation and Value Chains*, (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016). <https://doi.org/10.2791/658931>

⁵ J. Puukka, *Spreading Excellence & Widening Participation in Horizon 2020. Analysis of FP participation patterns and research and innovation performance of eligible countries European Commission*, (Luxembourg, 2018). <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/87f7b96d-c5ed-11e8-9424-01aa75ed71a1>

⁶ R. Radosevic and K. Ciampi Stancova, "External dimensions of smart specialisation: Opportunities and challenges for trans-regional and transnational collaboration in the EU-13", *JRC Research Reports JRC96030*, (Joint Research Centre, 2015). <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ipt/iptwpa/jrc96030.html>

⁷ E. Uyarra, Marzocchi C. and J. Sorvik, "How outward looking is smart specialisation? Rationales, drivers and barriers", *European Planning Studies*, Vol. 26, No. 12 (2018), pp. 2344–2363. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2018.1529146>

In contemporary academic discourse, particular importance is placed on research by scholars who believe that policy should promote a balanced approach, encouraging both local development and international interaction to create comprehensive innovation ecosystems. For instance, Yeates and Voogsgeerd⁸ analyse the EU's approach to social protection in trade relations, highlighting the role of the private sector in interregional interactions. Furthermore, Telò⁹ investigates the multidimensional structural features of multi-level global governance, proposing the concept of “competitive regionalism” to counteract authoritarianism and hierarchy.

Stychynska et al.¹⁰ analysed European countries' practices regarding mechanisms of interaction within the “government-business-civil society” system in the context of European integration. Additionally, Rüländ¹¹ focuses on the institutional design of interregional forums, their functionality in the context of global governance, connections with policy areas, and inclusivity.

Riegner's¹² research concentrates on the legal perspectives of international relations, global governance, and regional cooperation. The scholar proposed outlines for a programme of socio-legal research on multi-regional governance and interregional interaction.

Radziyevska and Us¹³ contributed to the study of regionalism as a stimulating phenomenon that shapes global development and is a critical determinant for a sustainable future. Simultaneously, Pauls¹⁴ evaluates the potential application of EU sustainability measures and prudential exclusions in sustainable finance, describing both actual and potential impact channels.

⁸N. Yeates and H. Voogsgeerd, “Social security, social protection, GATS and the new generation of EU trade agreements”, in: *Research Handbook on European Social Security Law*, (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2023), pp. 380–396. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800886353.00027>

⁹M. Telò, “Regional diversity, interregional/transregional dialogues, and the new multilateralism”, in: *Regionalism and Multilateralism*, (Routledge, 2020), pp. 66–92. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003020400-6>

¹⁰ A. Stychynska, A. Kravchenko, O. Krasilnikova, N. Husieva and I. Kyzymenko, “Theoretical aspects of improvement of society-business-government cooperation in the context of European integration”, *Social and Legal Studies*, Vol. 1, No. 7 (2024), pp. 243–253. <https://doi.org/10.32518/sals1.2024.243>

¹¹ J. Rüländ, “Interregionalism: why and how regions interact”, in *Handbook on Global Governance and Regionalism*, (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2022), pp. 263–278. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377561.00029>

¹² M. Riegner, “Global governance and regionalism: legal perspectives”, in: *Handbook on Global Governance and Regionalism*, (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2022), pp. 85–100. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377561.00015>

¹³ S. Radziyevska and I. Us, “Regionalisation of the world as the key to sustainable future”, *E3S Web of Conferences*, Vol. 166 (2020), 13016. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202016613016>

¹⁴ S. N. Pauls, “Propagation and Justification of EU Sustainable Finance Measures through EU FTAs”, in: *EU Sustainable Finance and International Trade Law: Legality and Propagation of EU Sustainable Finance Regulation under GATS and Free Trade Agreements*, (Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024), pp. 221–262. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73853-1_5

Outhwaite¹⁵ argues that European transregional processes are accompanied by a range of institutional changes essential for achieving a high level of cross-border interaction. The author asserts that the results of the EU's external activities should be monitored and evaluated based on pre-defined, transparent, country-specific, and measurable indicators.

Matt et al.¹⁶ identified actions and guidelines for fostering Industry 4.0 integration and highlighted the role of key participants (companies, educational organisations, and regional policymakers) within the ecosystem. Additionally, the modern scholar De Lombaerde¹⁷ defines the main aspects of regional cooperation and integration under current conditions of transregional interaction, while Chirodea et al.¹⁸ propose solutions for optimising cross-border cooperation to enhance European territorial, economic, and social unity.

Castrycck-Naumann¹⁹ examines transregional connections within the European context and their influence on global dynamics. At the same time, Brie²⁰ synthesises European policies, programmes, mechanisms, and tools to develop specific neighbourly relations along the EU's borders. This idea was further developed by Barmaliou and Pawlak²¹, who consider promoting digital transition and digital society critical elements of the EU's international cooperation and partnerships.

Despite progress in research on effective innovation policy development and understanding regional paradigms, scholars must navigate these diverse factors to create reliable and adaptive innovative interregional collaborations based on interinstitutional cooperation.

¹⁵ W. Outhwaite, *Transregional Europe*, (Emerald Publishing Limited, 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78769-493-420201009>

¹⁶ D. T. Matt, M. Molinaro, G. Orzes and G. Pedrini, "The role of innovation ecosystems in Industry 4.0 adoption", *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, Vol. 32, No. 9 (2021), pp. 369–395. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-04-2021-0119>

¹⁷ P. De Lombaerde, "Introduction to the Handbook of Regional Cooperation and Integration: why, where, and so what?", in: *Handbook of Regional Cooperation and Integration*, (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2024), pp. 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800373747.00007>

¹⁸ F. Chirodea, L. Soproni and M. Marian, "European Union tools for the sustainable development of border regions", *Sustainability*, Vol. 16, No. 1 (2023), art. No. 388. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16010388>

¹⁹ K. Castrycck-Naumann, *Transregional Connections in the History of East-Central Europe*, Vol. 9, (Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110680515>

²⁰ M. Brie, "The Reform of the EU Neighbourhood Policies and Instruments in the Post-2020 Period", *Analele Universității din Oradea. Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene (RISE)*, Vol. XII (2020), pp. 129–143. <https://doi.org/10.58603/QBOT2359>

²¹ N. Barmaliou and P. Pawlak, *Operational guidance: the EU's international cooperation on cyber capacity building*, (European Commission, 2023). <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/76149>

The article aims to establish the peculiarities of inter-institutional interaction within the framework of transnational cooperation in the modern EU and identify promising directions for improving efficiency and regional cooperation in this context.

Materials and methods

The study utilised complementary general scientific theoretical methods, including analysis, synthesis, and abstraction. The integration of analysis and synthesis allowed for an objective and comprehensive examination of the strategic directions of interinstitutional interaction within the legal regulation of transregional cooperation. The analysis enabled the clarification of definitions and conceptual categories. Analytical differentiation within the framework of the global concept into specific components identified the structure and specifics of the research object, aiding in the distinction of essential elements from non-essential ones and facilitating the classification of priority principles of interinstitutional interaction.

Unlike analysis, synthesis combines individual components and properties identified through analysis into a unified whole. In this process, meaningful integration occurred, moving from identical and essential elements to differentiated and diverse ones, consolidating general and specific aspects into a single concept—transregional cooperation in the contemporary European environment.

The abstraction method was employed to identify theoretical generalisations, define vital categories and concepts, and formulate conclusions regarding priority development vectors of the phenomenon under study. Abstraction was applied as a process of cognitive detachment from standard properties of management technologies, concepts, and tools while highlighting the sought-after essential characteristics.

The methodological and theoretical basis of the work was formed by considering the priority principles of systemic research implementation using a comprehensive approach. Sector-specific publications, materials from industry-specific scientific and practical conferences on the subject matter, and statistical data supported the study.

Spatial and temporal indicators and the level of information reliability served as criteria for inclusion or exclusion. Recent studies and publications from reliable scientometric information databases were selected for the work.

The analysis framework also included the level of bias risk: brainstorming and cause-and-effect analysis methods were used to assess bias risk.

The alignment of the applied methods with the study's objectives was considered essential. In particular, analysis and synthesis served as tools for accumulating the most valuable scientific information, while abstraction enabled the interpretation of foreign studies within the context of the primary essence.

2: THE CONCEPT OF PARTNERSHIP POLICY

The legal regulation aimed at establishing partnership relations. The European Neighborhood and Partnership Policy includes programmes to promote the economic and social development of regions bordering the EU and stimulate cooperation with regions of

third countries. It provides the change in interregionalism. Litsegård and Mattheis²² rightly pointed out that interregionalism impacts existing regionalisms. Regional movements of civil society, triggered by interregional trade negotiations, are capable of exerting negative influences and even undermining the foundations of regional economic development.

The institutional consolidation of interregional cooperation was an essential trend in interinstitutional interactions. The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) supports investments in infrastructure, innovation, SME development, and other projects that contribute to regional economic growth. In this regard, Litsegård and Mattheis²³ gave an expressive example of the European STOP TTIP campaign, with counterparts in the USA, formed as a reaction against the Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership (TTIP) between the US and the EU.

2-1: EUROPEAN STRATEGY OF INTERACTION

Contemporary European legislation aimed to improve tools for exchanging experience and information. Interregional cooperation programmes include INTERREG and URBACT. As an EU programme, the INTERREG aims to support cooperation between regions of different EU countries. URBACT aims to exchange experience and knowledge between cities to improve their management and sustainable development. Litsegård and Mattheis²⁴ appropriately marked tensions and controversies between the EU and the AU (neighbouring to the EU African Union), strengthening a perception of 'us' and 'them', positively affecting regional unity.

African leaders have repeatedly framed their EU counterparts as paternalistic and unable to consider the AU an equal partner. At the same time, the EU has lamented a lack of political will on the part of African policymakers. Hence, interregionalism in climate change and the environment can potentially consolidate regional actorness in Africa and Europe through cooperation and antagonism²⁵.

Legal regulation of transregional cooperation ensures the formation of coordination and coordination structures. The EU has various committees, forums, and coordination structures, such as the Committee of the Regions, that provide coordination and advisory support for interregional cooperation. The European territorial cooperation regulation determines the contribution of each member state to the system of transnational cooperation. In this context, the share of cross-border cooperation should be somewhat

²² A. Litsegård and F. Mattheis, "Broadening the concept of interregionalism: beyond state-centrism and Eurocentrism", *Third World Quarterly*, Vol. 45, No. 7 (2023), pp. 1273–1290. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2023.2274829>

²³ A. Litsegård and F. Mattheis, (2023).

²⁴ A. Litsegård and F. Mattheis, (2023).

²⁵ A. Litsegård and F. Mattheis, (2023).

reduced, while the share of maritime and transnational cooperation should increase, emphasising the interaction of the most remote regions²⁶.

2-2: SUBREGIONAL COOPERATION

The European practice of legal regulation takes into account the specificity of subregions. Subregional cooperation intensifies horizontal contacts within the EU and neighbouring countries. The EU has developed strategies for macro-regions such as the Danube region and the Baltic Sea. These strategies are aimed at solving everyday problems and exploiting joint opportunities. It is worth noting that in locations where the programme operates to support peace and reconciliation, active efforts are being made to promote socio-economic and regional stability in the respective regions²⁷.

The development of permanent mechanisms of grant cooperation is an essential tool for the legal regulation of transregional cooperation. The EU provides various grants and funding for projects to strengthen interregional cooperation. These funds can be used to implement joint initiatives in transport, energy, environmental protection and other areas²⁸.

3: CHALLENGES OF GEOPOLITICAL CRISIS PHENOMENA

The legal framework of transregional cooperation ensures the stability of transregional relations. Transregional cooperation in the European Union (EU) in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war has become essential for ensuring regional stability and security. Strengthening cooperation between EU regions and their neighbours aims to overcome the challenges associated with the conflict and support Ukraine. The proposal for the regulation on European territorial cooperation requires both participating states and third countries or partner countries to formally confirm their agreement with the content of the Interreg programme in writing before its submission to the Commission. It is worth noting that the agreement will include commitments to ensure the co-financing of the programme by participating countries, as well as commitments regarding the financial contribution of third parties²⁹.

In the conditions of the Russian-Ukrainian war, transregional cooperation takes on new dimensions. Through the ERDF and European Social Fund (ESF) programmes, the EU allocates significant funds to help Ukrainian refugees arriving in EU member states. The interinstitutional relations researcher Barbora Poyner gives a relevant opinion of Gabriel Price, CEO of the Romanian energy exchange BRM, who said that he has always believed that the countries in the region need to know each other better and cooperate to solve their problems. This is precisely what the SEEGAS project aims to do, so BRM has confidently

²⁶ European Union. *Proposal for a Regulation of The European Parliament and of The Council on specific provisions for the European territorial cooperation goal (Interreg) supported by the European Regional Development Fund and external financing instruments*, (European Union, 2021). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52018PC0374&from=SV>

²⁷ European Union. (2021).

²⁸ European Union. (2021).

²⁹ European Union. (2021).

joined the first proposal. We are optimistic that solutions will be developed quickly to facilitate cross-border gas flows and create a functional regional market³⁰.

The flexibility of the European legal principles of transregional cooperation ensures the activity of contacts at the local level. Special funds and initiatives are being created to support local communities hosting refugees to ensure their integration and socio-economic support. Poyner³¹ also appeals to Piotr Kuś's opinion (Deputy Director of Gas Market Development Division of Polish gas TSO GAZ-SYSTEM). Optimistic prospects for cooperation with regional partners and the Energy Community within the framework of the SEEGAS initiative were noted.

3-1: DEFENSE COOPERATION

Defence cooperation has become a key area of transregional interinstitutional cooperation. The EU is strengthening security and defence cooperation through the European Defense Fund (EDF) and Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) programmes. Cooperation with NATO and other international organisations aims to coordinate efforts to ensure security and counter hybrid threats. Barbora Poyner mentioned Oleksii Dubovskiy (Chairman of the Exchange Committee of the Ukrainian Energy Exchange (UEEX) position: “Within the framework of SEEGAS, we have received a great opportunity to not only significantly improve our mechanisms and eliminate bottlenecks that prevented the development of cross-border trade in the region and within each country, in particular, but also to unify them by EU standards”³².

The stability of Ukraine as an actor in international relations and a party to the confrontation with the Russian aggressor is ensured by innovative legal norms. The EU provides macro-financial assistance to Ukraine to stabilise its economy and rebuild war-damaged infrastructure. Stimulating economic cooperation and trade between EU countries and Ukraine through association agreements and free trade zones has become a significant part of interinstitutional interactions. The purpose of the EU Regulation 2021/947 (as pointed out by Article 21 TEU) is to ensure consistency between the different areas of its external action and between these and its other policies, as well as to work for a high degree of cooperation in all fields of international relations³³.

³⁰ B. Poyner, *Energy Community Secretariat supports trans-regional cooperation on development of integrated SEEGAS market*, (Energy-Community, July 21, 2021). <https://www.energy-community.org/news/Energy-Community-News/2021/07/21.html>

³¹ B. Poyner, (2021).

³² B. Poyner, (2021).

³³ EU monitor. *Regulation 2021/947 – Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument – Global Europe*, (EU Monitor, 2021). https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j4nvk6yhcbpeywk_j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vljn7p7icqyt

3-2: ENERGY STRATEGIES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Energy is a powerful object of efforts to improve the legal conditions of transregional cooperation. It is strengthening energy infrastructure and diversifying energy sources to reduce dependence on Russian energy resources. Supporting Ukraine in restoring and modernising its energy infrastructure has reliable legal grounds. According to Regulation 2021/947, the primary objective of the Union's development cooperation policy, as laid down in Article 208 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), is the reduction and, in the long term, the eradication of poverty.

The Union's development cooperation policy also contributes to the objectives of the Union's external action, in particular, to foster the sustainable economic, social and environmental development of developing countries, with the primary aim of eradicating poverty, as set out in point (d) of Article 21(2) TEU³⁴.

4: PROSPECTS FOR INTER-INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

Cyber security is also one of the leading factors in increasing the effectiveness of transregional cooperation between Ukraine and the EU in the face of Russian invasion. Increasing investment in the development of digital infrastructure and strengthening cybersecurity. Cooperation in information exchange and technology to protect against cyber attacks.

Regulation 2021/947 of the European Commission directed the establishment of precise monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, which are required to ensure appropriate accountability and transparency in the implementation of the Union's budget and to enable the effective assessment of progress in achieving the objectives of the Instrument³⁵.

The Transregional cooperation acquires an authentic expression due to the flexibility of legal regulation in media interaction. The development of exchange programmes and cultural and educational initiatives seeks to strengthen mutual understanding and solidarity between the peoples of the EU and Ukraine.

In addition, support for media and information campaigns is being strengthened to counter disinformation and propaganda. These measures strengthen ties between EU regions and their neighbours, increasing resilience and solidarity in the current conflict. It is important to note that continued and strengthened trans-regional cooperation will contribute to the stability and prosperity of the entire European region in the long term.

³⁴ EU monitor, (2021).

³⁵ EU monitor, (2021).

CONCLUSION

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Therefore, the EU legal regulation of inter-institutional interaction allows the modern EU to establish a list of instruments that will increase the stability of interstate relations and determine the prospects and further development trajectory of a united Europe. Creating transparent indicators of joint technical practices approaches for transnational labour and enshrining them in legal documents makes it possible to establish uniform game rules for all participants. Unifying transactions is also ensured, making it possible to plan activities for an extended period. Modern legal regulation in EU countries provides neighbouring countries with a road map for the modernisation of regional development for high-quality interaction with EU regions in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. EU legislation ensures the intensification of regional cooperation, increasing Ukraine's stability and potential in the fight against the aggressor in modernising public administration. Modern EU legislation provides planned indicators of development, considering the diversity of the definition of leadership industries and the distribution of positive experience. A wide range of tasks for optimising European legislation regarding transregional cooperation allows for solving issues from the energy sector to transferring resources from cross-border or land cooperation to arranging maritime transport corridors.

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